

Synthesis and Antitubercular Activity of Some 2-Aryl-3-[4-chlorobenzamido]-5-substituted-4-thiazolidinones

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2-Aryl-3-[4-chlorobenzamido]-5-substituted-4-thiazolidinones (II, III and IV) have been prepared by condensation of Schiff bases (I) with mercaptoalkanoic acids. These compounds show antitubercular activity against $H_{37}R_v$ strain.

THIAZOLIDINONES are well known for their varied spectrum of pharmacological activities¹⁻⁴.

Some of the substituted thiazolidinones have been found to possess anaesthetic, anticonvulsant, antitubercular and sedative properties^{5,6}.

A wide variety of carboxyhydrazides has been examined for antitubercular activity. The results obtained vary drastically depending on the strain of *Mycobacteria* used, and emphasize the need for using a human strain, such as $H_{37}R_v$, in screening for a potential antitubercular agent for human use. Benzoylhydrazide and its nitro-, chloro- and methoxy-derivatives have been rated active against the bovine strain D_4 , not significantly active against the bovine revental strain, and active against the human strain $H_{37}R_v$.

Since the advent of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) as a clinically effective antitubercular drug, a large number of hydrazides have been synthesised and tested for antibacterial properties⁸⁻¹⁰. Hydrazones obtained from hydrazides frequently act as monoamineoxidase (MAO) inhibitors. Besides, hydrazides have been associated with anthelmintic and antifungal activity^{11,12}.

The preparation of hydrazone from 4-chlorobenzamide involved the condensation of 4-chlorobenzamide with substituted aromatic aldehydes. The condensation was accomplished by heating the former with appropriate aldehyde in aqueous ethanol for a definite length of time to get the hydrazone.

The present work deals with the synthesis and pharmacological studies of some 4-thiazolidinones¹³ of the type II, III and IV, the Schiff¹⁴ bases of 4-chlorobenzamide with substituted aromatic aldehyde and condensed with mercapto alkanolic acid, viz. thioglycolic, thiomalic and thiolactic acids. When tested, these compounds (II, III and IV) showed antitubercular activity against $H_{37}R_v$ strain in Lowenstein-Jensen egg medium (4 ml).

The schematic presentation of the reaction sequences are given below.

(II), (III) and (IV)

Where R = Different aromatic moiety,
R' = CH_2COOH , CH_3 or H.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds have been determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The purity of synthesised compounds were checked by thin layer chromatography and infrared spectra (KBr), recorded on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. The structure of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, counter synthesis mixed melting point and infrared spectrum. The ir spectra of compounds II, III and IV showed characteristic bands at 1640, 1600 and 1650 cm^{-1} of carbonyl stretching frequency for thiazolidinone ring system.

1-[4-Chlorobenzoyl]-2-benzylidene hydrazine (I): To a solution of aldehyde (0.01 M) in ethanol (50 ml, 95%) was added 4-chlorobenzamide

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS II, III AND IV

Sl. No.	R	R'	Type of compd.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antitubercular activity*, $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$		
						0	5	30
1.	C_6H_5	H	II	190	73	+	+	-
2.	$2\text{-NO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$	H	II	166	71	+	+	-
3.	$4\text{-NO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$	H	II	187	68	+	+	-
4.	$4\text{-CH}_2\text{O-C}_6\text{H}_4$	H	II	198	70	+	+	-
5.	$3,4\text{-(CH}_2\text{O)}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3$	H	II	111	75	+	+	-
6.	C_6H_5	CH_2COOH	III	240	59	+	+	-
7.	$2\text{-NO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$	CH_2COOH	III	260	53	+	+	-
8.	$4\text{-NO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$	CH_2COOH	III	240	55	+	+	-
9.	$4\text{-CH}_2\text{O-C}_6\text{H}_4$	CH_2COOH	III	177	62	+	+	-
10.	$3,4\text{-(CH}_2\text{O)}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3$	CH_2COOH	III	140	51	+	+	-
11.	C_6H_5	CH_3	IV	88	65	+	+	-
12.	$2\text{-NO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$	CH_3	IV	218	58	+	+	-
13.	$4\text{-NO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$	CH_3	IV	96	62	+	+	-
14.	$4\text{-CH}_2\text{O-C}_6\text{H}_4$	CH_3	IV	191	63	+	+	-
15.	$3,4\text{-(CH}_2\text{O)}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3$	CH_3	IV	800	56	+	+	-

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

* (+) = Inactive (no inhibition), (-) = active.

zide (0.01 M)¹⁵ in ethanol (50 ml, 95%). The solution was heated for 2.5 h, cooled and worked up to get the corresponding Schiff base, I (62%), m.p. 226° (Found: N, 11.2. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 10.83%).

2-Phenyl-3-[4-chlorobenzamido]-4-thiazolidinone (II): 1-[4-Chlorobenzoyl]-2-benzylidene hydrazine (0.01 M), dry benzene (100 ml) and thioglycolic acid (0.012 M) were heated under reflux for 30 h using Dean and Stark water-separator. The solvent was removed by distillation and the residue was treated with NaHCO_3 solution and filtered. The thiazolidinones crystallised from 95% ethanol (73%), m.p. 191° (Found: N, 8.54; S, 9.78. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 8.42; S, 9.63%).

2-[4-Nitrophenyl]-3-[4-chlorobenzamido]-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones (III): 1-[4-Chlorobenzoyl]-2-[4-nitro]-benzylidene hydrazine (0.01 M) and thiomalic acid (0.01 M) were condensed in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h, temperature was then raised to 180° for 30 min. The product so obtained was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution (4 N) and filtered. The filtrate was reprecipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallised from 95% ethanol (55%), m.p. 240° (Found: N, 9.67; S, 7.41. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires N, 9.64; S, 7.35%).

2-[4-Methoxyphenyl]-3-[4-chlorobenzamido]-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinones (IV): 4-Methoxy benzaldehyde (0.02 M) was mixed with a solution of 1-[4-chlorobenzoyl]-2-[4-nitro]-benzylidene hydrazine (0.02 M) in dry benzene and refluxed for 2 h. Thiolic acid (0.02 M) was then added, and refluxing continued for further 6 h. The organic layer was washed with NaHCO_3 solution to remove unreacted thiolactic acid, and the solvent removed under reduced pressure to get the residue which on crystallisation from 95% ethanol gave the product (56%), m.p. 191° (Found: N, 7.54; S, 8.42. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ requires N, 7.44; S, 8.63%).

Biological screening: The *in vitro* antimycobacterial activity of the synthesised compounds have been studied at 0, 5 and 30 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (solvent: DMF)

against H_{37}R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* using Lowenstein-Jensen egg medium (4 ml). The retardation of growth rate has been studied upto 6 weeks at 37°. The procedure was duplicated using only solvent for control purpose.

The physical and biological data have been reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The screening results of the *in vitro* antimycobacterial activity of the synthesised compounds show that all are inactive at 0 and 5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration, but the title compounds (II, III and IV) are active at higher concentration, viz. at 30 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

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